

Synthesis of 2-Bromo-5-acyl-hydroquinones

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Synthetic methods to prepare the title compounds are described.

INTEREST in halogen containing aromatic hydroxyketones has arisen due to their strong bacteriostatic activities¹. These compounds are usually synthesised by the well-known methods such as Friedel and Craft's reaction or Fries' reaction. A number of halogen substituted acyl phenols have been reported in the literature by several workers²⁻⁵. These compounds are mainly prepared by subjecting esters of halogenated phenols to Fries' reaction; however very few esters of substituted hydroquinones appear to have been subjected to this reaction so far. Mauthner⁶ has observed that Fries reaction of 2-methoxy-hydroquinone diacetate gives 2-acetyl-5-methoxy-hydroquinone (4-methoxy-quinacetophenone). Russian workers⁷ have also reported similar observation in the case of 2:6-dinitro-hydroquinone monoacetate. Recently Shah and coworkers⁸ have synthesised 2-chloro and 2-bromo-quinacetophenones by the use of Fries reaction from the acetates of 2-chloro and 2-bromo-hydroquinone

It has been observed in this Laboratory⁹ that Fries reaction gives better yields of 2-acyl-hydroquinones as compared with the yields obtained by Friedel and Craft's reaction; hence the former reaction was investigated in the present work to prepare 2-bromo-5-acyl-hydroquinones.

- I. R = -CH₃.
- II. R = -CH₂CH₃.
- III. R = -CH₂-CH₂-CH₃.
- IV. R = -CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-CH₃.

Diesters of 2-bromo-hydroquinone were prepared by the usual procedure using the respective anhydride or acid chloride and were purified either by crystallisation or distillation under reduced pressure. Fries

reaction of these esters was conducted at 170°-180° usually for 2 hr. The corresponding ketones were isolated in pure condition and characterised by preparing their semicarbazones. The preparations of 2-bromo-5-acetyl, 2-bromo-5-propionyl, 2-bromo-5-*n*-butyryl and 2-bromo-5-*n*-valeryl-hydroquinone and their semicarbazones are described in the experimental

All these 2-bromo-5-acyl-hydroquinones gave Pyman's test¹⁰ for *o*-hydroxyketones and also gave intense violet colouration with 1% ferric chloride solution.

Experimental

2-bromo-hydroquinone: It was prepared by brominating hydroquinone according to the procedure described by Sarauw¹¹, m.p. 113° (Sarauw (*loc. cit.*) reports m.p. 111°-113°).

2-bromo-hydroquinone diacetate: 2-bromo-hydroquinone (10 g.) was suspended in freshly distilled acetic anhydride (6 ml) and the mixture was heated on a waterbath for 2 hr. On cooling the mixture was poured in ice water, when the ester solidified. The solid was filtered, washed with water and air dried. Yield 7 g. It was crystallised from pet. ether (40°-60°), m.p. 70°. (Lit.¹² gives m.p. 71°-73°).

2-bromo-hydroquinone dipropionate: 2-bromo-hydroquinone (10 g) was treated with freshly distilled propionyl chloride (16 g.) under anhydrous conditions at room temperature. After the reaction had subsided, the mixture was heated on a water bath for 3 hr. On cooling the mixture was added to water and kept overnight, when the ester solidified. It was filtered, washed with water and air dried. Yield 16 g. It was crystallised from pet. ether (60°-80°), m.p. 58°-59° (Found: Br, 26.2; Calc. for C₁₂H₁₃BrO₄; Br, 26.58 percent.).

2-bromo-hydroquinone di-*n*-butyrate: It was prepared by acylation of 2-bromo-hydroquinone (10 g.) with *n*-butyryl chloride (13 g.) according to the procedure described under 2-bromo-hydroquinone dipropionate. 2-bromo-hydroquinone di-*n*-butyrate had b.p. 230°-234°/80 mm. Yield 6 g. (Found:

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Br, 24.1; Calc. for $C_{14}H_{17}BrO_4$: Br, 24.32 percent.).

2-bromo-hydroquinone di-n-valerate: It was prepared from 2-bromo-hydroquinone (10 g.) and freshly distilled *n*-valeryl chloride (15 g.) according to the procedure mentioned in the above example. The ester had b.p. 237°–242°/15 mm. Yield 9.2 g. (Found: Br, 22.26; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{21}BrO_4$: Br, 22.40 percent.).

Fries' rearrangement of 2-bromo-hydroquinone diacetate: (Preparation of 2-bromo-5-acetyl-hydroquinone: I.).

The diester (5 g.) was mixed with freshly powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.) thoroughly and the mixture was placed in a hard glass tube fitted with calcium chloride guard tube. It was gradually heated to 170° for 2 hr. Temperature was then raised to 180° for 10 min. The contents were allowed to cool and were added to cold water acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid (1:1). The solid was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in 5% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution was filtered and the filtrate after cooling to 0° was acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid (1:1) to congo red. 2-bromo-5-acetyl-hydroquinone separated as a yellow solid. It was filtered, washed free from acid and air dried. Yield 2.8 g. It was crystallised from pet. ether (60°–80°) m.p. 148°–149°. (Found: Br, 34.42; Calc. for $C_9H_7BrO_3$: Br, 34.63 percent.). It gave positive Pyman's test (*loc. cit.*) and an intense violet colour with 1% ferric chloride solution.

Shah and coworkers (*loc. cit.*) reported m.p. of 2-bromo-5-acetyl-hydroquinone as 133°; hence it was prepared according to the procedure described by the above authors. The melting point of the product obtained by their procedure was found to be 148° after two crystallisations, and it did not depress the m.p. of the product obtained in the present work.

2-bromo-5-acetyl-hydroquinone was characterised by preparing its semicarbazone, m.p. 218°–219° (dil. ethanol (1:1)). (Found: Br, 27.2; N, 14.3; Calc. for $C_9H_{10}BrN_3O_3$: Br, 27.77; N, 14.57 percent.).

The following 2-bromo-5-acyl-hydroquinones were prepared according to the procedure described under the preparation of 2-bromo-2-acetyl-hydroquinone and characterised by preparing their semicarbazones.

2-bromo-5-propionyl-hydroquinone (II) crystallised from pet. ether (60°–80°) in the form of needles, m.p. 110°–111°. (Found: Br, 32.8; Calc. for $C_9H_9BrO_3$: Br, 32.65 percent.). Its *semicarbazone* had m.p. 256°–257° (dil. ethanol). (Found: Br, 26.7; N, 13.6; Calc. for $C_{10}H_{12}BrN_3O_3$: Br, 26.5; N, 13.91 percent.).

2-bromo-5-n-butyryl-hydroquinone (III) crystallised from pet. ether (60°–80°) (charcoal) as yellow granular crystals, m.p. 98°–99°. (Found: Br, 30.7; Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}BrO_3$: Br, 30.88 percent.). Its *semicarbazone* had m.p. 198° (ethanol). (Found: Br, 25.0; N, 13.4; Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}BrN_3O_3$: Br, 25.31; N, 13.3 percent.).

2-bromo-5-n-valeryl-hydroquinone (IV) crystallised from pet. ether (60°–80°), m.p. 70°–71°. (Found: Br, 28.9; Calc. for $C_{11}H_{13}BrO_3$: Br, 29.3 percent.). Its *semicarbazone* had m.p. 208°–209°. (Found: Br, 24.5; N, 12.5; Calculated for $C_{12}H_{16}BrN_3O_3$: Br, 24.25; N, 12.73 percent.).

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